

Stepwise gatekeeping procedures with retesting for multiplicity problems with two sequences of hypotheses

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Abstract

It is increasingly common nowadays to evaluate two doses of an investigational product in late phase clinical development to provide dosing flexibility. To enhance the product label, it is routine to include a primary and one or more secondary endpoints for multiplicity control. We describe stepwise gatekeeping procedures with retesting in this context. We show that the closure-based procedure constructed using the enhanced mixture method dominates the stepwise gatekeeping procedure with retesting when truncated Holm or truncated Hochberg procedures are used as the component multiple testing procedures for each family of hypotheses for a given endpoint. The stepwise procedure is equivalent to closure-based procedure when truncated Holm procedures are used as the component procedures provided that the sequence of truncation parameters are nonincreasing. We demonstrate through simulation studies that the proposed stepwise method remains highly efficient relative to the uniformly more powerful closure-based mixture method when truncated Hochberg procedures are used as the component procedures. Closed-form expressions for the adjusted p -values of elementary hypotheses based on the stepwise gatekeeping procedures with retesting are also provided.

Keywords: Closed testing, gatekeeping, mixture, retest, stepwise

1 Introduction

It is increasingly common nowadays to evaluate two doses of an investigational product in late phase clinical development to provide dosing flexibility. To enhance the product label, it is routine to include a primary and one or more secondary endpoints in confirmatory clinical trials. Strong control of the Type I error rate over all multiplicity components that may correspond to regulatory claims is often required [1, 2] to ensure reproducibility of significant findings. Graphical approaches [3, 4, 5, 6] and gatekeeping procedures [7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16] are flexible tools to account for the hierarchical structure of the null hypotheses of interest.

For multiplicity problems with multiple sequences of hypotheses (see the schizophrenia trial example depicted in Figure 1 of [11], the hypertension trial example depicted in Figure 2 of [12], and the chronic obstructive pulmonary disease [COPD] trial example depicted in Figure 2 of [15]), we often identify the families of hypotheses with the hierarchically ordered endpoints. Each family comprises of the multiple null hypotheses associated with the comparisons of the multiple doses of the investigational product to the common control for a given endpoint. There are natural serial logical restrictions among the hypotheses within each sequence. The hypotheses associated with higher ranked endpoints serve as gatekeepers for those associated with lower ranked endpoints within each sequence. Standard mixture gatekeeping procedures are introduced in [12, 14], modified mixture gatekeeping procedures are described in [15], and enhanced (α -exhaustive) mixture gatekeeping procedures are formulated in [16].

As pointed out in [15], a stepwise representation of gatekeeping procedure is desirable from a practical perspective since it facilitates the interpretation of the decision rules and communication of the results to product development teams and regulatory reviewers. Stepwise gatekeeping procedures with retesting are derived in [17] for Bonferroni parallel gatekeeping without considering serial logical restrictions among the hypotheses. For two sequences of hypotheses with serial logical restrictions, stepwise gatekeeping procedures without retesting are studied in [15]. Given the power advantage of

the enhanced mixture gatekeeping procedures, we introduce the closely-related stepwise gatekeeping procedures with retesting in the context of multiplicity problems with two sequences of hypotheses.

2 Stepwise gatekeeping procedures with retesting

We define the stepwise gatekeeping procedures in general multiplicity problems with two sequences of hypotheses grouped into m families as follows. Assume for simplicity that all component procedures used in a stepwise gatekeeping procedure are derived using the same multiple testing method, e.g., the Holm or Hochberg methods (note that the Hommel procedure is equivalent to the Hochberg procedure in multiplicity problems with two sequences of hypotheses). Let $\mathcal{P}(\gamma_i)$ denote the component procedure used in Family F_i for $i = 1, \dots, m$, where γ_i is the prespecified truncation parameter such that $0 \leq \gamma_i < 1$ for $i < m$ (to ensure separability [10]) and $\gamma_m = 1$. The rejection regions of truncated Holm and truncated Hochberg procedures are depicted in Figure 1 for two null hypotheses.

A general stepwise gatekeeping procedure based on enhanced mixture method utilizes the following testing algorithm:

1. Step 1. The null hypotheses in Family F_1 are tested using $\mathcal{P}(\gamma_1)$ at the full α .
2. Step i ($i = 2, \dots, m$). Consider the following two cases:
 - If both null hypotheses are rejected in Family F_{i-1} , the null hypotheses in Family F_i are tested using $\mathcal{P}(\gamma_i)$ at the full α .
 - If only one null hypothesis is rejected in Family F_{i-1} , the corresponding null hypothesis in Family F_i is tested using a univariate test at $\alpha(1 - \max(\gamma_s, \dots, \gamma_{i-1}))/2$, where s is the index of the first family in the sequence with a single rejected hypothesis.
3. Retesting step. If only one null hypothesis is rejected in Families F_s, \dots, F_m and $s < m$, go back to Family F_s to retest the nonrejected hypothesis in the other sequence at the full α . If this hypothesis is rejected, continue through families F_{s+1}, \dots, F_m until no more hypothesis in the sequence can be rejected at the full α .

Since potentially more null hypotheses can be rejected in the retesting step, the proposed stepwise gatekeeping procedure dominates the original stepwise gatekeeping procedure without retesting in [15]. To illustrate the proposed stepwise gatekeeping procedure, consider the multiplicity problem depicted in Figure 2, where the two sequences denote the two doses of an experimental treatment and the three families correspond to the primary endpoint and the two key secondary endpoints, respectively. Suppose that the raw p-values for the six null hypotheses are $p_1 = 0.0013$, $p_2 = 0.0075$, $p_3 = 0.0023$, $p_4 = 0.0247$, $p_5 = 0.0049$, and $p_6 = 0.1110$. Let $\alpha = 0.025$, $\gamma_1 = \gamma_2 = 0.6$ for the truncated Hochberg procedures for Families F_1 and F_2 . Then $\alpha/2 = 0.0125$, $(1 + \gamma_i)\alpha/2 = 0.02$ for $i = 1, 2$. By the right panel of Figure 1, since $\max(p_1, p_2) \leq (1 + \gamma_1)\alpha/2$, we reject both H_1 and H_2 in Family F_1 . Since $p_3 \leq \alpha/2$ and $p_4 > (1 + \gamma_2)\alpha/2$, we only reject H_3 in Family F_2 . We then test H_5 in Family F_3 using a univariate test at $(1 - \gamma_2)\alpha/2 = 0.005$, which results in the rejection of H_5 . The stepwise gatekeeping procedure described in [15] would stop here, while the proposed stepwise gatekeeping procedure would go back to Family F_2 to retest H_4 at the full α , which leads to the rejection of H_4 . Since $p_6 > \alpha$, H_6 cannot be rejected. In this example, the proposed stepwise gatekeeping procedure with retesting rejects one more null hypothesis than the original stepwise gatekeeping procedure without retesting. The same conclusion would be drawn had we used the Holm-based stepwise procedures.

It is shown in Proposition 1 that general stepwise gatekeeping procedures with retesting introduced above protect the global familywise error rate (FWER) in multiplicity problems with two sequences of null hypotheses.

Proposition 1 *A stepwise gatekeeping procedure with retesting for multiplicity problems with two sequences of hypotheses provides strong control of the global FWER.*

We prove Proposition 1 by constructing a closure-based procedure which dominates the stepwise gatekeeping procedure, i.e., every null hypothesis rejected by the stepwise procedure is also rejected by the closure-based procedure. This closure-based procedure is defined using the enhanced mixture method introduced in [16] and controls the global FWER.

Let H_1, \dots, H_n denote the n null hypotheses corresponding to the primary and secondary objectives in a clinical trial. The hypotheses are grouped into m families labeled F_1, \dots, F_m . Let N_k denote the index set of n_k hypotheses in Family F_k , $k = 1, \dots, m$, and let N denote the index set of all hypotheses. The families are tested sequentially and the testing algorithm accounts for logical relationships among the null hypotheses. For multiplicity problems with two sequences of hypotheses, $F_k = \{H_{2k-1}, H_{2k}\}$, $N_k = \{2k-1, 2k\}$, $n_k = 2$, $k = 1, \dots, m$, and the testing algorithm must account for the serial logical restrictions within sequence $S_1 = \{1, 3, \dots, 2m-1\}$ and within sequence $S_2 = \{2, 4, \dots, 2m\}$. For example, for Figure 2, the hypothesis H_5 is restricted by the hypothesis H_3 , which, in turn, is restricted by the hypothesis H_1 , meaning that H_3 is testable only if H_1 is rejected, and H_5 is testable only if H_3 is rejected. Similar serial logical restrictions apply to the other sequence of hypotheses.

The enhanced mixture method is defined using the closed testing framework. Consider the closed family of all $2^n - 1$ nonempty intersections of the hypotheses H_1, \dots, H_n . An intersection hypothesis is defined as $H(I) = \bigcap_{i \in I} H_i$, where $I \subseteq N$ is the index set of hypotheses in the intersection. The local p -value $p(I)$ will be computed for each intersection hypothesis $H(I)$ within the closed family. By the closed principle [18], the adjusted p -value for the elementary hypothesis H_i , $i = 1, \dots, n$, is derived as the maximum over all local p -values associated with the intersections containing H_i , i.e., $\tilde{p}_i = \max_{I: i \in I} p(I)$, and the hypothesis H_i is rejected if $\tilde{p}_i \leq \alpha$.

To align with the set of serial logical restrictions, the hypothesis H_i can be rejected only if all hypotheses included in the serial set $R(i)$ are also rejected. For any intersection hypothesis $H(I)$ and corresponding index set I , let $I_i = I \cap N_i$ denote the set of hypothesis indices included in Family F_i , $i = 1, \dots, m$. The restricted index set I_i^* is defined as the subset of I_i consisting of hypotheses that are testable if all hypotheses H_j , $j \in I_1 \cup \dots \cup I_{i-1}$, are accepted, or, equivalently,

$$I_i^* = \{j \in I_i : R(j) \cap (I_1 \cup \dots \cup I_{i-1}) = \emptyset\}$$

The overall restricted index set for the selected intersection hypothesis $H(I)$ is defined as

$$I^* = I_1^* \cup \dots \cup I_m^*$$

Similarly, N_i^* is the subset of N_i consisting of hypotheses that are testable if all hypotheses H_j , $j \in I_1 \cup \dots \cup I_{i-1}$, are accepted, that is,

$$N_i^* = \{j \in N_i : R(j) \cap (I_1 \cup \dots \cup I_{i-1}) = \emptyset\}$$

By definition, $I_1^* = I_1$, $N_1^* = N_1$. Let k_i , k_i^* , and n_i^* denote the number of indices in the index sets I_i , I_i^* , and N_i^* , respectively.

For the intersection hypothesis $H(I)$, let ℓ denote the last family with nonempty restricted index set, that is, $I^* = I_1^* \cup \dots \cup I_\ell^*$. For the enhanced mixture method, the local p -value for $H(I)$ is given by

$$p(I) = \min \left[\frac{p_1(I_1^* | N_1^*)}{c_1(I^*)}, \dots, \frac{p_{\ell-1}(I_{\ell-1}^* | N_{\ell-1}^*)}{c_{\ell-1}(I^*)}, \frac{p_\ell^*(I_\ell^* | N_\ell^*)}{c_\ell(I^*)} \right] \quad (1)$$

Here, the family-specific p -value $p_i(I_i^* | N_i^*)$ is based on an appropriate component procedure, e.g.,

$$p_i(I_i^* | N_i^*) = \begin{cases} p_{i(1)} / \{\gamma_i / k_i^* + (1 - \gamma_i) / n_i^*\} & \text{for truncated Holm} \\ \min_{j=1, \dots, k_i^*} p_{i(j)} / \{\gamma_i / (k_i^* - j + 1) + (1 - \gamma_i) / n_i^*\} & \text{for truncated Hochberg} \\ \min_{j=1, \dots, k_i^*} p_{i(j)} / \{j \gamma_i / k_i^* + (1 - \gamma_i) / n_i^*\} & \text{for truncated Hommel} \end{cases}$$

where γ_i is the truncation parameter of the component procedure for Family F_i , and $p_{i(j)}$ denotes the j th ordered p -value among the k_i^* null hypotheses in I_i^* , $j = 1, \dots, k_i^*$. In addition, $p_\ell^*(I_\ell^* | N_\ell^*)$ denotes the p -value produced by the regular component procedure by setting $\gamma_\ell = 1$, which makes the enhanced mixture method α -exhaustive. The coefficients $c_i(I^*)$, $i = 1, \dots, m$, play the role of family weights and are given by $c_1(I^*) = 1$, and

$$c_i(I^*) = \begin{cases} c_{i-1}(I^*) (1 - \gamma_{i-1}) (n_{i-1}^* - k_{i-1}^*) / n_{i-1}^* & \text{if } k_{i-1}^* > 0 \\ c_{i-1}(I^*) & \text{if } k_{i-1}^* = 0 \end{cases}$$

for $i = 2, \dots, m$. The family weights are nonincreasing, reflecting the diminishing importance of the sequentially ordered families. Of note, if $I_i^* = \emptyset$ for some $i = 1, \dots, \ell - 1$, then the i th term in (1) is omitted from the right hand side.

The following result is proved in Appendix A.

Lemma 1 *For the enhanced mixture method, the local p -value for the intersection hypothesis $H(I)$ is identical to the local p -value for the restricted intersection hypothesis $H(I^*)$, i.e., $p(I) = p(I^*)$.*

It follows from Lemma 1 that $\tilde{p}_i = \max_{I:i \in I} p(I^*)$. For multiplicity problems with two sequences of hypotheses, I^* contains either one index, or two indices with one index from each sequence. In particular, for the hypothesis H_{2i-1} in sequence S_1 , there are four types of index sets I containing $2i-1$ as classified by the restricted index sets I^* , and the local p -values for the enhanced mixture method using the Holm or Hochberg component procedures are derived accordingly:

- a. $I^* = \{2j-1\}$ for $j \leq i$, in which case, $p(I^*) = p_{2j-1}$.
- b. $I^* = \{2j-1, 2k\}$ for $j \leq i$ and $k < j$, in which case, $p(I^*) = \min\left(\frac{2p_{2k}}{1+\gamma_k}, \frac{2p_{2j-1}}{1-\gamma_k}\right)$.
- c. $I^* = \{2j-1, 2j\}$ for $j \leq i$, in which case, $p(I^*) = 2p_{j(1)}$ for the Holm procedure, and $p(I^*) = \min(2p_{j(1)}, p_{j(2)})$ for the Hochberg procedure.
- d. $I^* = \{2j-1, 2k\}$ for $j \leq i$ and $k > j$, in which case, $p(I^*) = \min\left(\frac{2p_{2j-1}}{1+\gamma_j}, \frac{2p_{2k}}{1-\gamma_j}\right)$.

Similarly, for H_{2i} in sequence S_2 , we can classify the index sets I containing $2i$ based on the restricted index sets I^* and derive the corresponding local p -values. These results can be used to obtain the adjusted p -values for the elementary hypotheses and help prove the following proposition.

Proposition 2 *The closure-based procedure constructed using the enhanced mixture method dominates the stepwise gatekeeping procedure with retesting.*

Proposition 2 implies Proposition 1. The proof of Proposition 2 is given in Appendix B. Of note, the Hochberg-based stepwise gatekeeping method with retesting may be strictly less powerful than the corresponding closure-based mixture method. For example, consider the two-family two-sequence problem with $0 \leq \gamma_1 < 1$, $(1+\gamma_1)\alpha/2 < p_1 \leq \alpha$, $\alpha/2 < p_2 \leq \alpha$, and $p_{2k} \leq (1-\gamma_1)\alpha/2$ for $k = 2, \dots, m$, in which case, H_1 cannot be rejected by the stepwise procedure with retesting because no hypothesis can be rejected in Family F_1 using the truncated Hochberg procedure, but H_1 can be rejected by the enhanced mixture method because the adjusted p -value for H_1 based on the enhanced mixture method,

$$\tilde{p}_1 = \max\left[p_1, \min(2p_{1(1)}, p_{1(2)}), \max_{k=2, \dots, m} \min\left(\frac{2p_1}{1+\gamma_1}, \frac{2p_{2k}}{1-\gamma_1}\right)\right] \wedge 1$$

is less than or equal to α . Here, $a \wedge b = \min(a, b)$. On the other hand, we have the following proposition, which shows that the stepwise method with retesting is equivalent to the enhanced mixture method if the Holm procedures with nonincreasing truncation parameters are used as the component procedures. This result is proved in Appendix C.

Proposition 3 *The stepwise gatekeeping procedure with retesting is equivalent to the closure-based procedure constructed using the enhanced mixture method if truncated Holm procedures with nonincreasing truncation parameters $\gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_{m-1}$ are used as the component procedures for the first $m-1$ families and the regular Holm procedure is used as the component procedure for the last family.*

The expressions for adjusted p -values for elementary hypotheses based on the stepwise procedure with retesting are given in Proposition 4, which follow directly from the three cases for rejecting an elementary hypothesis by the stepwise procedure as outlined in Appendix B. This result is useful for numerical comparisons of the stepwise procedure with the closure-based procedure.

Proposition 4 *The adjusted p -values for H_{2i-1} and H_{2i} for the stepwise gatekeeping procedure with retesting are given by*

$$\tilde{p}_{2i-1} = \min\left[\max_{j=1, \dots, i} a_j, \min_{s=1, \dots, i} b_{is1} I\left(b_{is1} < \frac{2p_{2s}}{1+\gamma_s}\right), \min_{s=1, \dots, i \wedge (m-1)} c_{is1} I\left(c_{is1} < \frac{2p_{2s-1}}{1+\gamma_s}\right)\right] \wedge 1$$

and

$$\tilde{p}_{2i} = \min\left[\max_{j=1, \dots, i} a_j, \min_{s=1, \dots, i} b_{is2} I\left(b_{is2} < \frac{2p_{2s-1}}{1+\gamma_s}\right), \min_{s=1, \dots, i \wedge (m-1)} c_{is2} I\left(c_{is2} < \frac{2p_{2s}}{1+\gamma_s}\right)\right] \wedge 1$$

respectively, where

$$\begin{aligned}
a_j &= \max \left(2p_{j(1)}, \frac{2p_{j(2)}}{1 + \gamma_j} \right) \text{ for Holm, } a_j = \frac{2p_{j(2)}}{1 + \gamma_j} \text{ for Hochberg} \\
b_{is1} &= \max \left\{ \max_{j=1, \dots, s-1} a_j, \max_{j=s, \dots, i} \frac{p_{2j-1}}{d_{sj}} \right\} \\
b_{is2} &= \max \left\{ \max_{j=1, \dots, s-1} a_j, \max_{j=s, \dots, i} \frac{p_{2j}}{d_{sj}} \right\} \\
c_{is1} &= \max \left\{ \max_{j=1, \dots, s-1} a_j, \max_{j=s, \dots, m} \frac{p_{2j}}{d_{sj}}, \max_{j=s, \dots, i} p_{2j-1} \right\} \\
c_{is2} &= \max \left\{ \max_{j=1, \dots, s-1} a_j, \max_{j=s, \dots, m} \frac{p_{2j-1}}{d_{sj}}, \max_{j=s, \dots, i} p_{2j} \right\} \\
d_{sj} &= \frac{1 - \max(\gamma_s, \dots, \gamma_{j-1})}{2}
\end{aligned}$$

for $i = 1, \dots, m$, $s = 1, \dots, i$ and $j = s, \dots, m$. Here, we define $d_{ss} = 1/2$.

The above method for calculating the adjusted p -values for stepwise procedures is faster and more accurate than the grid search algorithm proposed in [15].

3 Examples

Hereafter, we will refer to the proposed stepwise gatekeeping procedure with retesting simply as the stepwise method, and the closure-based enhanced mixture gatekeeping procedure simply as the mixture method. Given the equivalence of the Holm-based stepwise and mixture methods, we will compare the following three methods in the order of increasing statistical efficiency: the Holm-based stepwise method, the Hochberg-based stepwise method, and the Hochberg-based mixture method. We will use the same value of the truncation parameters for the first $m - 1$ families and vary the value of the truncation parameters from 0 to 0.9 by 0.1 to assess the sensitivity of results to the value of the truncation parameters.

3.1 Example 1

Consider Case study 1 in [16] based on a Phase III clinical trial for testing four null hypotheses grouped into two families as depicted in Figure 1 of [16]. Consider the following set of raw p -values, $p_1 = 0.02$, $p_2 = 0.002$, $p_3 = 0.001$, $p_4 = 0.005$. Figure 3 shows the adjusted p -values for the four hypotheses. For this case study, all three methods produced identical adjusted p -values. However, the adjusted p -values for H_1 , H_3 , and H_4 are rather sensitive to the value of the truncation parameter. The best results are obtained for $\gamma = 0$ (i.e., Bonferroni for Family F_1), and the worst results are obtained for $\gamma = 0.6$. It might seem counter-intuitive that the adjusted p -value for H_1 does not always improve when the truncation parameter γ increases. This can be attributed to the retesting of the stepwise method and the α -exhaustiveness of the enhanced mixture method. For example, for the mixture method, the adjusted p -value for H_1 is given by

$$\tilde{p}_1 = \max \left[p_1, q_1, \min \left(\frac{2p_1}{1 + \gamma}, \frac{2p_4}{1 - \gamma} \right) \right] \wedge 1$$

where $q_1 = 2p_{1(1)}$ and $q_1 = \min(2p_{1(1)}, p_{1(2)})$ for the Holm- and Hochberg-based mixture methods, respectively. Increasing the value of γ will decrease the value of $2p_1/(1 + \gamma)$, but increase the value of $2p_4/(1 - \gamma)$, and which one determines the minimum in the third term of \tilde{p}_1 depends on the relative magnitude of p_1 and p_4 . In our case, since $p_4 < p_1$, the minimum is given by $2p_4/(1 - \gamma)$ initially, thus increasing γ will increase the adjusted p -value, until we reach $\gamma = (p_1 - p_4)/(p_1 + p_4) = 0.6$, after which the minimum is given by $2p_1/(1 + \gamma)$, and increasing γ will decrease the adjusted p -value. Similarly, by Proposition 4, the adjusted p -value for H_1 produced by the Hochberg-based stepwise method is

$$\check{p}_1 = \min \left[\frac{2p_{1(2)}}{1 + \gamma}, 2p_1 I \left(2p_1 < \frac{2p_2}{1 + \gamma} \right), c_1 I \left(c_1 < \frac{2p_1}{1 + \gamma} \right) \right] \wedge 1$$

where $c_1 = \max\left(p_1, 2p_2, \frac{2p_4}{1-\gamma}\right)$ represents the retesting case, and increasing the value of γ will make it harder to reject H_4 after rejecting H_2 but not H_1 in Family F_1 , thus decreasing the probability of retesting H_1 .

Similar findings are obtained with the following set of raw p -values used in the hypertension trial example in [12], $p_1 = 0.029$, $p_2 = 0.012$, $p_3 = 0.031$, $p_4 = 0.013$, for which $\gamma = 0$ yields the best adjusted p -values and $\gamma = 0.4$ yields the worst adjusted p -values for the four elementary hypotheses.

3.2 Example 2

Consider the COPD trial example in [15], which compares two doses of a treatment with a placebo for a primary and three key secondary endpoints. The eight null hypotheses are grouped into two sequences and four families (see Figure 2 of [15]), and the following set of one-sided p -values for the dose-placebo tests is considered: $p_1 = 0.0194$, $p_2 = 0.0068$, $p_3 = 0.0271$, $p_4 = 0.0088$, $p_5 = 0.0370$, $p_6 = 0.0018$, $p_7 = 0.0814$, $p_8 = 0.0066$. Figure 4 shows the adjusted p -values for the eight hypotheses. For this case study, all three methods produced identical adjusted p -values. We again observed the rise and fall of the adjusted p -value for H_1 as the value of the truncation parameters increases. The adjusted p -values for hypotheses in subsequent families (e.g., H_6 and H_8) exhibit more complex patterns.

As an example where the three methods yield different adjusted p -values, consider the following set of one-sided p -values: $p_1 = 0.0171$, $p_2 = 0.0181$, $p_3 = 0.0012$, $p_4 = 0.0006$, $p_5 = 0.0049$, $p_6 = 0.0038$, $p_7 = 0.0024$, $p_8 = 0.0019$. With truncation parameters $\gamma_1 = \gamma_2 = \gamma_3 = 0.6$, the adjusted p -values are 0.0342 for each of the eight hypotheses for the Holm-based stepwise method, 0.0226 for each of the eight hypotheses for the Hochberg-based stepwise method, and 0.0190 for H_1 and H_3 and 0.0226 for the other six hypotheses for the Hochberg-based mixture method. In this case, the Holm-based stepwise method fails to reject any hypothesis, while the Hochberg-based stepwise and mixture methods reject all eight hypotheses at $\alpha = 0.025$. In addition, the Hochberg-based mixture method produces more significant adjusted p -values for H_1 and H_3 than the corresponding stepwise method.

4 Comparison of the stepwise and mixture methods

We present a simulation study to compare the power of the Hochberg-based stepwise method with the corresponding mixture method for multiplicity problems with two sequences of hypotheses grouped into three families (see Figure 2). Let θ_i denote the expected effect size for the test of the null hypotheses H_i , $i = 1, \dots, 6$. The effect size is defined as the mean treatment difference divided by the common standard deviation. To assess the potential power loss of the stepwise method relative to the mixture method, we consider the following simulation scenarios:

- Scenario 1 assumes that the treatment effect is present and identical across all endpoints and doses, i.e., $\theta_i = \theta$ for $i = 1, \dots, 6$.
- Scenario 2 assumes that the high dose has a larger treatment effect than the low dose across all endpoints, specifically, $\theta_i = \theta$ for $i = 1, 3, 5$, and $\theta_i = 0.75\theta$ for $i = 2, 4, 6$.
- Scenario 3 assumes that the treatment effect is present across the endpoints at the high dose only, i.e., $\theta_i = \theta$ for $i = 1, 3, 5$, and $\theta_i = 0$ for $i = 2, 4, 6$.

Similar to [15, 16], we assume a balanced design with 120 patients per treatment arm, a multivariate normal distribution for the test statistics with the correlation matrix given in Table 3 of [11] (i.e., $\rho_{12} = 0.8$, $\rho_{13} = 0.4$, and $\rho_{23} = 0.3$), and $\theta = 0.37$ to guarantee 80% marginal power for each test at a one-sided $\alpha = 0.025$. In addition, two different success criteria are considered as in [15, 16]:

- Criterion C1 is based on the probability to reject at least one null hypothesis in Family F_1 , at least one in Family F_2 , and at least one in Family F_3 .
- Criterion C2 is based on the probability to reject both null hypotheses in Family F_1 , both in Family F_2 , and at least one in Family F_3 .

Furthermore, three sets of truncation parameters in Families F_1 and F_2 are considered as in [15, 16]:

- Set 1: $\gamma_1 = \gamma_2 = 0$ to save a large amount of α for the secondary endpoints.

- Set 2: $\gamma_1 = \gamma_2 = 0.5$ to strike a fair balance of power between the primary and secondary endpoints.
- Set 3: $\gamma_1 = \gamma_2 = 0.8$ to put more weight on the primary and the first key secondary endpoints.

Table 1 presents the results of power comparisons based on 10,000 simulation runs. The stepwise method has almost the same power as the mixture method across simulation scenarios and sets of truncation parameters. The power loss is at most one percent.

Now we discuss the impact of the truncation parameters on the rejection probabilities for the individual hypotheses and the success probabilities for the two success criteria.

For Scenario 1, the two doses are equally effective, and increasing the value of the truncation parameters slightly increases the marginal power for H_1 and H_2 , has almost no impact on H_3 and H_4 , and slightly decreases the marginal power for H_5 and H_6 . In addition, there is a notable reduction in the power for the success criterion C1, while the increase in the power for the success criterion C2 is only slight.

For Scenario 2, the high dose is more effective than the low dose, and increasing the value of the truncation parameters slightly increases the marginal power for H_1 and H_2 , leads to relatively larger decreases in the marginal power for H_3 and H_5 , slightly increases the marginal power for H_4 , has virtually no impact on H_6 , has more notable reduction in the power for the success criterion C_1 , and has less increase in the power for the success criterion C2.

For Scenario 3, the low dose has no treatment effect, which leads to the very low probabilities for rejecting the null hypotheses H_2 , H_4 , or H_6 , and for succeeding on the success criterion C_2 . Increasing the value of the truncation parameters has no impact on the marginal power for H_1 but greatly reduces the marginal power for H_3 and H_5 and the success probability for C_1 . This can be explained as follows. Since the low dose has no treatment effect, there is little chance to reject H_2 , so that we need to have $p_1 \leq \alpha/2$ in order to reject H_1 , which, in turn, implies that we need to have $p_3 \leq (1 - \gamma)\alpha/2$ in order to reject H_3 after rejecting H_1 , and have $p_5 \leq (1 - \gamma)\alpha/2$ in order to reject H_5 after rejecting H_3 . Therefore, increasing the value of γ has no impact on rejecting H_1 but makes it harder to reject H_3 and H_5 .

5 Discussion

For multiplicity problems with two sequences of hypotheses, we have described a stepwise gatekeeping procedure with retesting, where the retesting step imitates the alpha-exhaustiveness property of the enhanced mixture gatekeeping procedure. We have shown analytically that the proposed stepwise method is equivalent to the closure-based enhanced mixture method when Holm procedures with nonincreasing truncation parameters are used as the component procedures. We have demonstrated through simulation studies that the proposed stepwise method remains highly efficient relative to the enhanced mixture method when Hochberg procedures are used as the component procedures. This is an important finding from a practical point of view because clinical trial researchers often have to choose between a less efficient procedure with easy-to-understand decision rules and a more efficient procedure which relies on more complex rules. Given the high relative efficiency retained by the proposed stepwise method relative to the more complex closure-based mixture method, we recommend its use to facilitate the interpretation of the decision rules and communications of the study results to both internal and external stakeholders.

Although it is of great interest to develop stepwise gatekeeping procedures for multiplicity problems with three or more sequences of hypotheses, it is pointed out in [15] that stepwise testing algorithms cannot be constructed in the general case. The closure-based enhanced mixture method [16] and general graphical approaches that account for correlations among the dose-placebo test statistics within each family [5] can be considered in this general setting and the performance of these two classes of multiple test procedures will be compared in future research.

To simplify the use of the proposed stepwise gatekeeping procedure for multiplicity problems with two sequences of hypotheses and facilitate the reporting of statistically significant results, we provide an R function to calculate the adjusted p -values for the elementary hypotheses in Appendix D.

Data availability statement

Data sharing not applicable to this article as no datasets were generated or analysed during the current study.

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A Proof of Lemma 1

We prove Lemma 1 using equation (2) in [16],

$$p(I) = p(I \cup \{j\}) \quad \text{if } \exists i \in I \cap R(j) \quad (2)$$

Let $I = I_1 \cup \dots \cup I_m$, $I^* = I_1^* \cup \dots \cup I_m^*$. By definition of restricted index sets, for any $j \in I_2 \setminus I_2^*$, there exists an $i \in I_1 \cap R(j)$. Applying (2) to $I = I_1 \cup (I_2 \setminus \{j\}) \cup I_3 \cup \dots \cup I_m$, we have

$$p(I) = p(I_1 \cup (I_2 \setminus \{j\}) \cup I_3 \cup \dots \cup I_m)$$

We continue in this fashion to eliminate all $j \in I_2 \setminus I_2^*$ to obtain

$$p(I) = p(I_1 \cup I_2^* \cup I_3 \cup \dots \cup I_m)$$

Similarly, if $j \in I_3 \setminus I_3^*$, then $\exists i \in (I_1 \cup I_2^*) \cap R(j)$. Applying (2) to $I = I_1 \cup I_2^* \cup (I_3 \setminus \{j\}) \cup \dots \cup I_m$, we have

$$p(I) = p(I_1 \cup I_2^* \cup (I_3 \setminus \{j\}) \cup \dots \cup I_m)$$

We continue in this fashion to eliminate all $j \in I_3 \setminus I_3^*$ to obtain

$$p(I) = p(I_1 \cup I_2^* \cup I_3^* \cup \dots \cup I_m)$$

This process can be continued until Family F_m , so that $p(I) = p(I_1 \cup I_2^* \cup \dots \cup I_m^*)$, which yields Lemma 1.

B Proof of Proposition 2

We prove Proposition 2 by demonstrating that every null hypothesis rejected by the stepwise procedure is also rejected by the closure-based procedure. By symmetry of the problem, we only need to show that if H_{2i-1} is rejected by the stepwise procedure, then H_{2i-1} is also rejected by the mixture method. There are three cases that can lead to the rejection of H_{2i-1} by the stepwise procedure:

1. Both $\{H_{2j-1}, H_{2j}\}$ are rejected by the component procedures for $j = 1, \dots, i$.
2. Both $\{H_{2j-1}, H_{2j}\}$ are rejected by the component procedures for $j = 1, \dots, s-1$, H_{2s-1} is rejected but H_{2s} is not rejected by the component procedure for Family F_s , and H_{2j-1} is rejected by the univariate test at $\alpha(1 - \max(\gamma_s, \dots, \gamma_{j-1}))/2$ for $j = s+1, \dots, i$, where $s \in \{1, \dots, i\}$ is the index of the first family in the sequence with a single rejected hypothesis.
3. Both $\{H_{2j-1}, H_{2j}\}$ are rejected by the component procedures for $j = 1, \dots, s-1$, H_{2s} is rejected but H_{2s-1} is not rejected by the component procedure for Family F_s , H_{2j} is rejected by the univariate test at $\alpha(1 - \max(\gamma_s, \dots, \gamma_{j-1}))/2$ for $j = s+1, \dots, m$, and H_{2j-1} is rejected by the univariate test at the full α for $j = s, \dots, i$.

We only need to show that $p(I^*) \leq \alpha$ for the four types of the restricted index sets I^* as described following Lemma 1 for each of the above three cases.

For case 1, by Figure 1, if the truncated Holm procedure is used for Family F_j , then $p_{j(1)} \leq \alpha/2$ and $p_{j(2)} \leq (1 + \gamma_j)\alpha/2$. If the truncated Hochberg procedure is used for Family F_j , then $p_{j(2)} \leq (1 + \gamma_j)\alpha/2$. Here $j = 1, \dots, i$. Since $p_{j(2)} \leq (1 + \gamma_j)\alpha/2$ regardless of the component procedure used for Family F_j , $p(I^*) \leq \alpha$ holds for type a of I^* as $p_{2j-1} \leq p_{j(2)}$, for type b of I^* as $p_{2k} \leq (1 + \gamma_k)\alpha/2$, for type c of I^* with the Hochberg procedure as $p_{j(2)} \leq \alpha$, and for type d of I^* of $p_{2j-1} \leq (1 + \gamma_j)\alpha/2$. For the Holm procedure, since $p_{j(1)} \leq \alpha/2$ for case 1, $p(I^*) \leq \alpha$ holds for type c of I^* .

For case 2, by Figure 1, rejection of H_{2s-1} but not H_{2s} by either the truncated Holm or truncated Hochberg component procedure for Family F_s implies that $p_{2s-1} \leq \alpha/2$ and $p_{2s} > (1 + \gamma_s)\alpha/2$. Obviously, $p(I^*) \leq \alpha$ holds for type a of I^* . For type b of I^* , $p(I^*) \leq \alpha$ holds for $k \leq s-1$ by the argument in case 1. For $k \in \{s, \dots, j-1\}$, since $p_{2j-1} \leq (1 - \max(\gamma_s, \dots, \gamma_{j-1}))\alpha/2 \leq (1 - \gamma_k)\alpha/2$, we also have $p(I^*) \leq \alpha$. For type c of I^* , $p(I^*) \leq \alpha$ holds for $j \leq s-1$ by the argument in case 1. For $j \in \{s, \dots, i\}$, since $p_{2j-1} \leq (1 - \max(\gamma_s, \dots, \gamma_{j-1}))\alpha/2 \leq \alpha/2$, we have $p(I^*) \leq \alpha$. Here, for convenience, we define $\max(\gamma_s, \dots, \gamma_{j-1}) = 0$ if $j = s$. For type d of I^* , $p(I^*) \leq \alpha$ holds for $j \leq s-1$ by the argument in case 1, and holds for $j \geq s$ because $p_{2j-1} \leq (1 - \max(\gamma_s, \dots, \gamma_{j-1}))\alpha/2 \leq (1 + \gamma_j)\alpha/2$.

For case 3, by Figure 1, rejection of H_{2s} but not H_{2s-1} by either the truncated Holm or truncated Hochberg component procedure for Family F_s implies that $p_{2s} \leq \alpha/2$ and $p_{2s-1} > (1 + \gamma_s)\alpha/2$. Obviously, $p(I^*) \leq \alpha$ holds for type a of I^* . For type b of I^* , $p(I^*) \leq \alpha$ holds for $k \leq s-1$ by the argument in case 1. If $k \in \{s, \dots, j-1\}$, since $p_{2k} \leq (1 - \max(\gamma_s, \dots, \gamma_{k-1}))\alpha/2 \leq (1 + \gamma_k)\alpha/2$, we have $p(I^*) \leq \alpha$. For type c of I^* , $p(I^*) \leq \alpha$ holds for $j \leq s-1$ by the argument in case 1. For $j \in \{s, \dots, i\}$, since $p_{2j} \leq (1 - \max(\gamma_s, \dots, \gamma_{j-1}))\alpha/2 \leq \alpha/2$, we have $p(I^*) \leq \alpha$. For type d of I^* , $p(I^*) \leq \alpha$ holds for $j \leq s-1$ by the argument in case 1, and holds for $j \geq s$ because $p_{2k} \leq (1 - \max(\gamma_s, \dots, \gamma_{k-1}))\alpha/2 \leq (1 - \gamma_j)\alpha/2$. This completes the proof of Proposition 2.

C Proof of Proposition 3

By Proposition 2, we only need to show that every null hypothesis rejected by the closure-based enhanced mixture gatekeeping procedure is also rejected by the stepwise gatekeeping procedure with retesting if Holm procedures with nonincreasing truncation parameters are used as the component procedures. By symmetry of the problem, we only need to show this for H_{2i-1} , which will be done by induction on i . By the discussion of the four types of restricted index sets I^* with $2i-1 \in I$ following Lemma 1, the adjusted p -value for the hypothesis H_{2i-1} produced by the enhanced mixture method using the Holm procedures is

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{p}_{2i-1} = & \max \left[\max_{j=1, \dots, i} p_{2j-1}, \max_{j=1, \dots, i, k=1, \dots, j-1} \min \left(\frac{2p_{2k}}{1 + \gamma_k}, \frac{2p_{2j-1}}{1 - \gamma_k} \right), \right. \\ & \left. \max_{j=1, \dots, i} 2p_{j(1)}, \max_{j=1, \dots, i, k=j+1, \dots, m} \min \left(\frac{2p_{2j-1}}{1 + \gamma_j}, \frac{2p_{2k}}{1 - \gamma_j} \right) \right] \wedge 1 \end{aligned}$$

In particular,

$$\tilde{p}_1 = \max \left[p_1, 2p_{1(1)}, \max_{k=2, \dots, m} \min \left(\frac{2p_1}{1 + \gamma_1}, \frac{2p_{2k}}{1 - \gamma_1} \right) \right] \wedge 1$$

If $\tilde{p}_1 \leq \alpha$, we would like to show that H_1 is rejected by the stepwise procedure with retesting. If $p_1 \leq p_2$, then the second argument of \tilde{p}_1 implies that $p_1 \leq \alpha/2$. By Figure 1, H_1 is rejected by the truncated Holm procedure for Family F_1 . If $p_1 > p_2$, the second argument of \tilde{p}_1 implies that $p_2 \leq \alpha/2$ and H_2 is rejected by the truncated Holm procedure for Family F_1 . If $p_1 \leq (1 + \gamma_1)\alpha/2$, then H_1 is also rejected by the truncated Holm procedure for Family F_1 . If $p_1 > (1 + \gamma_1)\alpha/2$, then the third argument of \tilde{p}_1 implies that

$$p_{2k} \leq (1 - \gamma_1)\alpha/2 = (1 - \max(\gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_{k-1}))\alpha/2$$

for $k = 2, \dots, m$, where the equation follows because the truncation parameters $\gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_{m-1}$ are nonincreasing. Therefore H_4, \dots, H_{2m} are rejected by the stepwise procedure. By the first argument of \tilde{p}_1 , $p_1 \leq \alpha$, hence H_1 is rejected in the retesting step of the stepwise procedure.

Now assume that $\tilde{p}_{2i-1} \leq \alpha$ implies the rejection of H_{2i-1} by the stepwise procedure with retesting. If $\tilde{p}_{2i+1} \leq \alpha$, then $\tilde{p}_{2i-1} \leq \tilde{p}_{2i+1} \leq \alpha$. By the induction assumption and Appendix B, we must have one of the following three cases that lead to the rejection of H_{2i-1} by the stepwise procedure:

1. Both $\{H_{2j-1}, H_{2j}\}$ are rejected by the component procedures for $j = 1, \dots, i$. This means that $p_{j(1)} \leq \alpha/2$ and $p_{j(2)} \leq (1 + \gamma_j)\alpha/2$ for $j = 1, \dots, i$.
2. Both $\{H_{2j-1}, H_{2j}\}$ are rejected by the component procedures for $j = 1, \dots, s-1$, H_{2s-1} is rejected but H_{2s} is not rejected by the component procedure for Family F_s , and H_{2j-1} is rejected by the univariate test at $\alpha(1 - \max(\gamma_s, \dots, \gamma_{j-1}))/2$ for $j = s+1, \dots, i$. This means that

$p_{j(1)} \leq \alpha/2$ and $p_{j(2)} \leq (1 + \gamma_j)\alpha/2$ for $j = 1, \dots, s-1$, $p_{2s-1} \leq \alpha/2$, $p_{2s} > (1 + \gamma_s)\alpha/2$, and $p_{2j-1} \leq (1 - \max(\gamma_s, \dots, \gamma_{j-1}))\alpha/2 = (1 - \gamma_s)\alpha/2$ for $j = s+1, \dots, i$, where the equation follows because the truncation parameters $\gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_{m-1}$ are nonincreasing.

3. Both $\{H_{2j-1}, H_{2j}\}$ are rejected by the component procedures for $j = 1, \dots, s-1$, H_{2s} is rejected but H_{2s-1} is not rejected by the component procedure for Family F_s , H_{2j} is rejected by the univariate test at $\alpha(1 - \max(\gamma_s, \dots, \gamma_{j-1}))/2$ for $j = s+1, \dots, m$, and H_{2j-1} is rejected by the univariate test at the full α for $j = s, \dots, i$. This means that $p_{j(1)} \leq \alpha/2$ and $p_{j(2)} \leq (1 + \gamma_j)\alpha/2$ for $j = 1, \dots, s-1$, $p_{2s} \leq \alpha/2$, $p_{2s-1} > (1 + \gamma_s)\alpha/2$, $p_{2j} \leq (1 - \max(\gamma_s, \dots, \gamma_{j-1}))\alpha/2 = (1 - \gamma_s)\alpha/2$ for $j = s+1, \dots, m$, and $p_{2j-1} \leq \alpha$ for $j = s, \dots, i$.

Consider case 1. If $p_{2i+1} \leq p_{2i+2}$, then the third argument of \tilde{p}_{2i+1} for $j = i+1$ implies that $p_{2i+1} \leq \alpha/2$. By the left panel of Figure 1, H_{2i+1} is rejected by the truncated Holm procedure for Family F_{i+1} . If $p_{2i+1} > p_{2i+2}$, then the third argument of \tilde{p}_{2i+1} for $j = i+1$ implies that $p_{2i+2} \leq \alpha/2$, hence H_{2i+2} is rejected by the truncated Holm procedure for Family F_{i+1} . If $p_{2i+1} \leq (1 + \gamma_{i+1})\alpha/2$, we reject both H_{2i+1} and H_{2i+2} by the truncated Holm procedure for Family F_{i+1} . If $p_{2i+1} > (1 + \gamma_{i+1})\alpha/2$, then H_{2i+2} is rejected but H_{2i+1} cannot be rejected by the truncated Holm procedure for Family $i+1$. On the other hand, the fourth argument of \tilde{p}_{2i+1} for $j = i+1$ implies that

$$p_{2k} \leq (1 - \gamma_{i+1})\alpha/2 = (1 - \max(\gamma_{i+1}, \dots, \gamma_{k-1}))\alpha/2$$

for $k = i+2, \dots, m$, where the equation follows because the truncation parameters $\gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_{m-1}$ are nonincreasing. Therefore, H_{2k} ($k = i+2, \dots, m$) are rejected by the stepwise procedure. Finally, the first argument of \tilde{p}_{2i+1} for $j = i+1$ implies that $p_{2i+1} \leq \alpha$, so that H_{2i+1} is rejected in the retesting step of the stepwise procedure.

Consider case 2. The second argument of \tilde{p}_{2i+1} for $j = i+1$ and $k = s$ along with $p_{2s} > (1 + \gamma_s)\alpha/2$ imply that $p_{2i+1} \leq (1 - \gamma_s)\alpha/2 = (1 - \max(\gamma_s, \dots, \gamma_i))\alpha/2$, hence H_{2i+1} is rejected by the stepwise procedure.

Consider case 3. The first argument of \tilde{p}_{2i+1} for $j = i+1$ implies that $p_{2i+1} \leq \alpha$, hence H_{2i+1} is rejected by the stepwise procedure. This completes the proof of Proposition 3.

D R function for obtaining adjusted p-values for the stepwise gatekeeping procedure

```
# row wise maximum of a matrix
rmax <- function(x) {
  x = as.matrix(x)
  if (ncol(x)==1) {
    value = x
  } else {
    value = as.matrix(apply(x, 1, max))
  }
  value
}

# row wise minimum of a matrix
rmin <- function(x) {
  x = as.matrix(x)
  if (ncol(x)==1) {
    value = x
  } else {
    value = as.matrix(apply(x, 1, min))
  }
  value
}
```

```

# gamma: truncation parameters for the m families
# test: HOLM or HOCHBERG component procedures
# retest: whether to allow retesting
fstp2seq <- function(p, gamma, test="HOCHBERG", retest=TRUE) {
  nreps = nrow(p)
  n = ncol(p)
  padj = matrix(NA, nreps, n)
  m = n/2

  a = matrix(NA, nreps, m)
  for (j in 1:m) {
    x = p[,c(2*j-1,2*j)]
    a[,j] = 2*rmax(x)/(1+gamma[j])
    if (toupper(test)=="HOLM") {
      a[,j] = rmax(cbind(2*rmin(x), a[,j]))
    }
  }

  d = matrix(NA, m, m)
  for (s in 1:m) {
    gmax = 0
    for (j in s:m) {
      if (j>s) gmax = max(gmax, gamma[j-1])
      d[s,j] = (1-gmax)/2
    }
  }

  for (i in 1:m) {
    t1 = rmax(a[,1:i])

    t2 = matrix(1, nreps, 1)
    for (s in 1:i) {
      lhs = matrix(0, nreps, 1)

      if (s>1) {
        lhs = rmax(cbind(lhs, a[,1:(s-1)]))
      }

      for (j in s:i) {
        lhs = rmax(cbind(lhs, p[,2*j-1]/d[s,j]))
      }

      rhs = 2*p[,2*s]/(1+gamma[s])

      ok = which(lhs < rhs)
      if (length(ok) > 0) {
        t2[ok] = rmin(cbind(t2[ok], lhs[ok]))
      }
    }

    if (retest & (m>1)) {
      t3 = matrix(1, nreps, 1)
      for (s in 1:min(i,m-1)) {
        lhs = matrix(0, nreps, 1)

        if (s>1) {

```

```

    lhs = rmax(cbind(lhs, a[,1:(s-1)]))
  }

  for (j in s:m) {
    lhs = rmax(cbind(lhs, p[,2*j]/d[s,j]))
  }

  for (j in s:i) {
    lhs = rmax(cbind(lhs, p[,2*j-1]))
  }

  rhs = 2*p[,2*s-1]/(1+gamma[s])

  ok = which(lhs < rhs)
  if (length(ok) > 0) {
    t3[ok] = rmin(cbind(t3[ok], lhs[ok]))
  }
}

padj[,2*i-1] = rmin(cbind(t1, t2, t3))
} else {
  padj[,2*i-1] = rmin(cbind(t1, t2))
}

t2 = matrix(1, nreps, 1)
for (s in 1:i) {
  lhs = matrix(0, nreps, 1)

  if (s>1) {
    lhs = rmax(cbind(lhs, a[,1:(s-1)]))
  }

  for (j in s:i) {
    lhs = rmax(cbind(lhs, p[,2*j]/d[s,j]))
  }

  rhs = 2*p[,2*s-1]/(1+gamma[s])

  ok = which(lhs < rhs)
  if (length(ok) > 0) {
    t2[ok] = rmin(cbind(t2[ok], lhs[ok]))
  }
}

if (retest & (m>1)) {
  t3 = matrix(1, nreps, 1)
  for (s in 1:min(i,m-1)) {
    lhs = matrix(0, nreps, 1)

    if (s>1) {
      lhs = rmax(cbind(lhs, a[,1:(s-1)]))
    }

    for (j in s:m) {
      lhs = rmax(cbind(lhs, p[,2*j-1]/d[s,j]))
    }
  }
}

```

```

for (j in s:i) {
  lhs = rmax(cbind(lhs, p[,2*j]))
}

rhs = 2*p[,2*s]/(1+gamma[s])

ok = which(lhs < rhs)
if (length(ok) > 0) {
  t3[ok] = rmin(cbind(t3[ok], lhs[ok]))
}

padj[,2*i] = rmin(cbind(t1, t2, t3))
} else {
  padj[,2*i] = rmin(cbind(t1, t2))
}
}

padj
}

```

Table 1: Simulation results for the Hochberg-based stepwise gatekeeping procedures with retesting and the enhanced mixture gatekeeping procedures, where γ is the value of the truncation parameters for Families F_1 and F_2 .

Scenario	γ	Method	Power (%)							
			Success criterion		Null hypothesis					
			C1	C2	H1	H2	H3	H4	H5	H6
1	0.0	Stepwise	71	55	77	77	70	69	59	59
		Mixture	71	55	77	77	70	70	60	59
	0.5	Stepwise	69	56	78	78	70	69	58	58
		Mixture	69	56	78	78	70	70	59	58
	0.8	Stepwise	66	57	79	79	69	69	57	57
		Mixture	66	57	79	79	69	69	57	57
2	0.0	Stepwise	58	34	75	52	67	42	55	29
		Mixture	59	35	75	52	68	42	56	29
	0.5	Stepwise	54	35	76	53	65	42	51	29
		Mixture	54	35	76	53	65	43	51	29
	0.8	Stepwise	49	35	76	54	62	43	47	29
		Mixture	49	35	77	54	62	43	47	29
3	0.0	Stepwise	53	1	74	3	66	1	53	0
		Mixture	53	1	74	3	66	1	53	0
	0.5	Stepwise	44	1	74	3	60	1	44	0
		Mixture	44	1	74	3	60	1	44	0
	0.8	Stepwise	32	1	74	3	51	1	32	0
		Mixture	32	1	74	3	51	1	32	0

Figure 1: Rejection regions for the truncated Holm (left) and truncated Hochberg (right) procedures with two hypotheses, where p_1 and p_2 are the raw p-values for testing H_1 and H_2 , respectively, and γ is the truncation parameter.

Figure 2: Multiplicity problem with three families of hypotheses in two sequences.

Figure 3: Adjusted p -values for the elementary hypotheses based on the stepwise gatekeeping procedure with retesting and the enhanced mixture method in Example 1. Here γ is the truncation parameter of the Holm or Hochberg component procedures for Family F_1 , and the three methods yield identical adjusted p -values for the nominal p -values $p_1 = 0.02$, $p_2 = 0.002$, $p_3 = 0.001$, $p_4 = 0.005$.

Figure 4: Adjusted p -values for the elementary hypotheses based on the stepwise gatekeeping procedure with retesting and the enhanced mixture method in Example 2. Here γ is the truncation parameter of the Holm or Hochberg component procedures for Families F_1 , F_2 , and F_3 , and the three methods yield identical adjusted p -values for the nominal p -values $p_1 = 0.0194$, $p_2 = 0.0068$, $p_3 = 0.0271$, $p_4 = 0.0088$, $p_5 = 0.0370$, $p_6 = 0.0018$, $p_7 = 0.0814$, $p_8 = 0.0066$.